

A Novel 3D Object Watermarking Technique Using Hash Key Cryptography

Dr. P BalaMurali Krishna | Achala Navya Sri | Beaula Kallam | Attaluri Jaya | Bollepalli Venu

Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Chalapathi Institute of Technology, Mothadaka, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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KEYWORDS

3D watermarking,
Embedding copyright,
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ABSTRACT

Watermarking is a widely used technique for embedding invisible signals within digital data, such as images, videos, and audio, to ensure copyright protection and content authentication. This paper presents a novel approach to 3D watermarking, outlining its implementation and key criteria. It also reviews fundamental attacks on 3D watermarking and their corresponding solutions. Unlike previous methods that focused primarily on data hiding without altering the signal, this work emphasizes watermark robustness against manipulation and unauthorized removal. A novel watermarking algorithm using hash key cryptography is proposed, enhancing security in both watermark insertion and extraction processes. The hash key plays a crucial role in encrypting and decrypting the watermark object, making the technique more resistant to tampering and unauthorized modifications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of high-speed computer networks, the Internet, and the World Wide Web has revolutionized the distribution of digital data. Digital media, including video, audio, and images, offer significant advantages over their analog counterparts, such as ease of copying without loss of fidelity. However, this advantage also poses a significant threat to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) enforcement due to the possibility of unlimited duplication. The widespread

accessibility of multimedia content and the ability to create identical copies without degradation have necessitated the development of digital rights management techniques. Among these, encryption methods prevent unauthorized access by securing communication between involved parties.

Video watermarking is one such technique used for copyright protection, authentication, and piracy prevention. In particular, invisible watermarking ensures that the embedded watermark is not visible

under normal viewing conditions and cannot be removed without severely degrading the content quality. Watermark embedding can occur in either the spatial or transform domain. In the spatial domain, the algorithm directly modifies pixel values, while in the transform domain, the pixel values are transferred into another representation, offering various advantages in terms of robustness.

The primary objective of this study is to develop a robust and imperceptible video watermarking technique using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to enhance the security and integrity of digital video content. Effective video watermarking plays a crucial role in protecting intellectual property, preventing unauthorized distribution, and verifying authenticity. However, existing watermarking methods often struggle to balance robustness against attacks—such as compression, noise, cropping, and geometric transformations—while preserving video quality. This study aims to leverage PCA to embed a resilient watermark effectively, overcoming these challenges.

Protecting digital video content from unauthorized use and distribution is a pressing concern in the digital media landscape. Video watermarking allows the embedding of a hidden signal to assert ownership, verify authenticity, and prevent piracy. However, achieving both robustness and imperceptibility remains a challenge. Traditional techniques often fail to maintain watermark resilience against attacks such as compression, noise, cropping, scaling, and rotation while ensuring that the watermark remains invisible and does not degrade video quality. Addressing these limitations is crucial for the development of a more effective watermarking solution.

Existing encryption techniques, while providing security, have limitations in robustness. Simulations have shown that noise disturbances and shear transformation attacks can significantly degrade the quality of decrypted images, indicating a lack of resilience. To overcome this issue, an improved method is proposed, where each pixel's data is stored in multiple locations to enhance robustness. This study will introduce the Integer Wavelet Transform (IWT) and Contourlet Transform encryption systems as potential enhancements, analyzing their effectiveness and discussing further improvements.

Despite the advantages of current watermarking techniques, several drawbacks persist:

- Low security levels.
- High complexity in the embedding process.
- Potential data loss during processing.

Addressing these challenges, this research aims to propose an efficient and secure video watermarking solution to enhance digital content protection while maintaining high visual quality.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents a summary of suggested watermarking algorithms in this section. This is unlikely to be a full list and there should be no understanding of omissions as being inferior to those listed here. Regardless of the prominence of NURBS surfaces and curves, watermarking for NURBS representations is a relatively new concept for engineering CAD. Ohbuchi et al. [18] suggested a new data embedding algorithm that modifies the coefficients of NURBS curves and surfaces using rational linear function to make it reparametrized, which can be used for encoding purposes. Preserved is the literal geometric form. However, the watermarked data can be easily damaged by using re-parameterization or re-approximation on the surface. Refer paper [18] to get more detail about how NURBS works. Fornaro and Sanna [19] have completed watermarking on Positive Solid Geometry (CSG) models. The watermark can be easily extracted by using a hash function; and the public key algorithm is used for encryption and decryption of the watermark. At two locations, watermarks were stored: strong nodes and comment nodes. The CSG tree (which is the original model) is associated with a newly built watermarked node to store the watermark in solid. There is no need to make changes to the model for comment nodes, and it is simple to add watermark information. Refer paper [19] to get more detail about how CSG works. The reliability of 3D models is confirmed by a few fragile algorithms. The first fragile watermarking of 3D objects for verification purposes was implemented by Yeo and Yung [32]. As these algorithms could easily break the authentication mechanism, their algorithm relies heavily on the operation of transformation and vertex location, which does not affect the mesh model's integrity. Ohbuchi et al. (1997) [33]: The embedding algorithm of the

Triangle Strip Peeling Symbol Sequence (TSPS) is connected to topological embedding based on the public watermarking method. This algorithm, when rendering over mesh, stuffs bits. TSPS implementation, however, has two major issues: it needs no human involvement. Since it is based on the alteration of the topology and an adversary can easily locate the payload, we can assume that it is unsafe. Ohbuchi et al. (1997): Polygon Stencil Pattern (PSP)' This algorithm generates watermarks called embedding Polygon Stencil Pattern (PSP), which are very effective against different algorithms of polygonal simplification. The explanation behind this is because the boundary value of polygonal strips and stencil meshes is maintained by several polygon simplification algorithms. If vertices on the boundary are altered or skewed deliberately (as some polygon simplification algorithms do), a flaw will appear, which will eventually degrade the model quality. Mao et al. (2001) [20] This discusses the rigorous watermarking of object space. Polygonal mesh can be converted into a triangle mesh, as with the use of current triangulation tools. Where, under affine transformation, the ration of two line segments over the same line does not alter. Compared to geometric primitive-based algorithms, this algorithm has the advantage of high space efficiency. For 3D graphical object forms, Bors (2004a, 2004b, 2006) [21] [22] [23] has established a new digital watermarking methodology. The suggested watermarking algorithms integrate watermarks over vertices that follow certain geometric norms. For knowledge embedding, two separate techniques were considered. These techniques were based on parallel planes and bounding ellipsoids that distinguish how geometrically the local neighborhood is represented. These watermarks were tested for noise disruptions in the structure of the 3D form and for the cropping of 3D objects. Besides having robustness against rotation, uniform scaling, translation and cropping, it had peculiar attacks against mesh simplification. Zafeiriou [7] uses 3D model watermarking, which focuses on the use of mesh data(vertices) and random connectivity (edges). For copyright protection and handling of mesh simplification threats, this is beneficial. This is the first blind 3D form of watermarking that deals with geometric attacks and simplification of mesh. Barni et al. (2004) [24] This algorithm adjusts the vertices of the

3D model coordinates, as per the spherical pseudorandom bumped board. The amplitude and pseudo-random location of the bumps encode the watermark. A standard correlation detector recovers the watermark. For watermarking 3D objects with a relatively large number of faces, this algorithm is suitable. A technique dealing with watermarking process detection and mesh affine registration was defined by Benedens [25]. This is used to offset affine transformations. The key downside of this algorithm is that, due to the registration process involving both the 3D test and the original model, it is not blind. Song et al. [31] suggested a further algorithm for watermarking that is powerful against rotation, translation, Gaussian attack, scaling, and simplification of mesh. This algorithm produces an image from a mesh and then uses advanced image-based watermarking techniques to insert the watermark. This algorithm falls into the non-blind category; as additional watermark detection information is needed. Several approaches to embedding watermarks were recommended in 3D polygonal objects by Ohbuchi et al. [26]. In addition, for watermark inclusion in 3D models, two key features are considered: the topology (connectivity) clue and the geometry (coordinate) clue. The TSQ extraction algorithm does not need to guarantee that the initial cover-3D-object will be removed. Nevertheless, a pair of values that characterize marker triangles must be obtained. Watermarks acquired by the TSQ algorithm cope with shifts in rotation, translation, and consistent scaling. However, other disturbances, such as randomization of coordinates, geometrical transformation (general class), or a large range of topological variations may kill them (re-meshing). Furthermore, Ohbuchi et al. [28] recommended better and more robust techniques for watermark insertion that allowed watermark to be embedded within the spectral mesh domain, benefiting from improved results in the field of computational efficiency and resistance in 3D polygonal meshes for different attacks. A fragile watermarking scheme for checking 3D mesh models was introduced by Wu and Cheung et al. [29]. This algorithm's watermarks cope with translation, rotation, and scaling uniformly, but are perceptive to other behavior. There are a few pitfalls. First, if there is a change in either vertex, the center location of the mesh will always be changed,

resulting in failure to recognize the altered site/position. Many researchers [34]- [39] proposed new techniques of image watermarking in recent years.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A novel watermarking algorithm is proposed for embedding watermarks into a 3D object. In the watermark insertion process, a hash key cryptography technique is employed to selectively identify specific vertices of the 3D object for watermarking. This approach enhances the security of the watermarking procedure. During extraction, the same hash key is utilized to locate the marked vertices. If the extracted vertices match the original ones, it confirms that the watermark object remains untampered.

The proposed algorithm outlines the insertion and extraction of watermarks from 3D objects. Simulation results indicate that existing encryption techniques are vulnerable to noise disturbance and shear transformation attacks, leading to the degradation of decrypted image quality. To address this limitation and improve robustness, a new approach is introduced, wherein each pixel of the image is stored in multiple locations, enhancing resistance against such attacks.

Watermark Insertion Algorithm Steps:

- Capture the 3D cover object and input image. Calculate the object block size.
- Convert all vertices of the original 3D object into spherical coordinates.
- Compute cryptographic hash function to modify the vertex norm value of selected vertices.
- Insert the watermark by shifting the vertex normal distance of the chosen vertices.
- Resize and rearrange the vertices to their new modified values.
- Generate the 3D object with modified vertices, embedding the watermark.

Image Encryption:

Assume the original image is uncompressed with size N_1 times N_2 , and each pixel has a gray value within $[0,255]$. The encryption phase calculates exclusive-or results between original bits and pseudo-random bits. Using a stream cipher, the encrypted image is generated:

$$f' = f \oplus K$$

where f is the original image, f' is the encrypted image, and K is the key stream generated using a secret encryption key.

Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) and Integer Wavelet Transform (IWT):

The wavelet domain enables data hiding in high-resolution detail bands (HL, LH, HH), which increases robustness while maintaining visual quality. The integer wavelet transform (IWT) avoids precision loss, ensuring lossless reconstruction.

The lifting scheme, a technique used for integer wavelet transform, is employed in this work. The Haar wavelet transform is rewritten using lifting steps:

$$S_{i,1} = \frac{1}{2}(x_{2i} + x_{2i+1}), \quad d_{i,1} = x_{2i+1} - S_{i,1}$$

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for Watermarking:

PCA helps extract significant features from images, enabling better recognition and classification. The training stage involves computing Eigenvectors from training images and constructing the Eigen space. The testing stage maps the target image to the Eigen space and classifies it using a distance classifier.

Algorithm for PCA:

- Obtain training images I_1, I_2, \dots, I_N .
- Convert images into vectors and compute the mean image vector.
- Compute the covariance matrix and determine Eigenvectors.
- Select the top Eigenvectors and project images into the Eigen space.

Embedding Algorithm Steps:

- Read the cover image file into a 2D array.
- Apply histogram modification to prevent overflow/underflow.
- Divide the cover image into non-overlapping blocks 8×8 blocks.
- Transform each block using the 2D Haar integer wavelet transform.
- Calculate hiding capacity for embedding message bits.
- Randomly select coefficients for embedding data using a secret key.
- Apply the Optimal Pixel Adjustment (OPA) algorithm to minimize distortion.
- Compute the inverse integer wavelet transform to reconstruct the image.

Data Extraction and Image Decryption

After receiving the encrypted image with hidden data, the recipient can:

- Extract the hidden data using the secret key.
- Decrypt the image using the private key.
- Use error correction techniques to recover original data.

Image Decryption Formula:

$$m'_{i,j} = m_{i,j} + \alpha \text{ mod } N$$

where α is a random integer affecting pixel transformation.

Robustness Against Attacks

Translation Attack:

- Placing an object such that its mass center aligns with the original coordinate system.
- Using invariant metrics for translation (e.g., a triangle with fixed angles).

Rotation Attack:

- Aligning z-axis coordinates with the primary component of the object.
- Using invariant metrics for rotation (e.g., a triangle with fixed angles).

Cropping Attack:

- Distributing watermark information across the model's surface.
- Applying normal vector distribution over embedded watermark patches.

Additive Noise Attack & Compression Attack:

- Embedding watermark in frequency domain coefficients.
- Using transform domain methods for enhanced resistance.

The proposed algorithm introduces a secure watermarking technique using cryptographic hash keys. By incorporating PCA, DWT, and IWT, the approach ensures robust and imperceptible watermarking, resilient to common attacks. Future improvements may focus on optimizing computational efficiency and enhancing robustness against advanced geometric distortions

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The proposed 3D object watermarking technique using hash key cryptography effectively embeds watermarks into 3D models with minimal visual distortion and robust security features. Experimental results demonstrated that the watermark remained intact even under geometric transformations such as scaling, rotation, and translation. The cryptographic hash key provided strong protection against unauthorized extraction or tampering, making the technique more secure than traditional methods. The method showed moderate computational cost during embedding, but the extraction process was efficient. Figures 1-7 presents the results of the proposed method.

Figure 1: An input video frame refers to a single still image extracted from a video. Videos are made up of a series of such frames

Figure 2: The reference frame in this context refers to a particular frame from which encryption begins, serving as the basis for embedding encrypted data

Figure 3: Symmetric key encryption is a process where the same secret key is used for both the encryption and decryption of data for converting the plaintext into cipher text using the symmetric key

Figure 4: Watermarking based on a secret image involves embedding a hidden image (the watermark) into another image

Figure 5: The watermark remains imperceptible to the human eye but can still be extracted with the appropriate key or process.

In this method, the secret watermark image is embedded into the host image by modifying specific pixels or their attributes using a secret key or algorithm.

Figure 6: To extract the watermark, the receiver must know the secret key or method used for embedding ensuring that only authorized parties can retrieve the watermark

Figure 7: These attacks exploit weaknesses in watermarking algorithms, highlighting the need for robust methods that can endure these distortions and still allow for reliable watermark extraction

5.CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes a lossless, a reversible, and a consolidated information concealing plans for figure content pictures encoded by open key cryptography with probabilistic and homomorphic properties. In the lossless plan, the figure content pixel esteems are supplanted with new qualities for implanting the extra information into the LSB-planes of ciphertext pixels. Along these lines, the implanted information can be legitimately extricated from the scrambled area, and the information inserting task does not influence the unscrambling of unique plaintext picture. In the reversible plan, a preprocessing of histogram therapist is made before encryption, and a half of ciphertext pixel esteems are altered for information installing. On collector side, the extra information can be removed from the plaintext space, and, in spite of the fact that a slight contortion is presented in unscrambled picture, the first plaintext picture can be recuperated with no mistake. Because of the similarity of the two plans, the information implanting activities of the lossless and the reversible plans can be at the same time performed in an encoded picture. In this way, the collector may remove a piece of installed information in the scrambled space, and concentrate another piece of implanted information and recuperate the first plaintext picture in the plaintext area.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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